

TALENT TRAINING AFFECTING OPERATION MANAGEMENT OF CHEERLEADING COMPETITION EVENT IN YUNNAN PROVINCE

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Abstract

With the popularization and rapid development of Cheerleading in Yunnan Province, Cheerleading competitions at all levels in Yunnan Province have been carried out, and gradually become mature. This study aims to explore the development and management of Cheerleading Events in Yunnan Province. It emphasizes the importance of sports management dynamics, focusing on factors such as organizational structure, talent training, event training, and operational management. This study has an in-depth understanding of the Operation Management system, improves and standardizes the management mechanism, so as to promote the sustainable development of Yunnan Cheerleading event. So as to provide a theoretical basis for the high-quality development of Yunnan province Cheerleading competition in the future. The method used was a mixture of qualitative and quantitative research methods, using semi-structured in-depth interviews with experts. Quantitative research in the form of questionnaire survey to collect data of research participants, using the method of statistical analysis to analyze the questionnaire collected data, including descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and regression analysis, the research question for a comprehensive exploration, for the region Cheerleading event Operation Management provides valuable insights. The results show that: 1) Discuss the relationship between the variables in the model through a focus group composed of relevant experts in Cheerleading events. Through the discussion, the influencing factors affecting the Operation Management of Yunnan Province Cheerleading Events are determined. 2) This study shows that the organizational structure, talent training, event training and Operation Management have a significant influence, and there is a positive correlation with each other. 3) Focus group meeting with our team of Cheerleading event Operation Management experts not only validates the core structure of our quantitative model, but also provides key improvements and new ways to explore.

Keywords: Talent Training; Cheerleading Competition Event; Operation Management; Yunnan Province.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2009, the state general administration of sports officially approved for the national Cheerleading league official events, the Cheerleading event presents a blowout development trend, Yunnan Cheerleading sports belongs to the top development across the country, the construction of the Operation Management system, help to form a series of related Cheerleading sports development, can cause the attention of more people, and can form a benign interaction mode. It will also promote the development of the Chinese Cheerleading movement to a new level. So, what are the main problems in the Operation Management of Cheerleading Events in Yunnan Province? Is there a new management model suitable for the operation of Cheerleading Events in Yunnan Province? This paper will in Yunnan province Cheerleading event Operation Management as the breakthrough point, multi-angle,

wide range, in Cheerleading event Operation Management on the basis of the present situation of investigation and study, in-depth investigation and analysis, find out the situation for the Yunnan Province Cheerleading competition to point out a new development direction, grasp the inherent law of project development, mining Yunnan province Cheerleading event Operation Management of effective resources, establish and perfect the reasonable management mechanism, to promote the healthy development of Cheerleading event. It is hoped to provide reference basis and countermeasures for the wider development of Cheerleading competition in Yunnan province.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Related theories and concepts

This paper involves several important theoretical studies. (1) The first important theory is the organizational structure, that is, how to divide the division of labor, grouping and coordination, and institutionalize organizational activities through the division and establishment of different functional departments and the distribution of different powers. Zhou (2018) studied the scientific management of human resources, mastered the comprehensive skills and talents, used the flexible leadership method to promote the realization of the club's strategic goals, timely adjusted the development strategy and organizational structure, strengthened the supervision of the implementation of the system, and formed a complete human resources system. Its organizational structure has an important influence on the management of Cheerleading activities in Yunnan Province.(2) The first important theory is organizational structure, which is how to divide the labor, group and coordination of work tasks, and institutionalize organizational activities through the division of different levels, the establishment of different functional departments and the distribution of different powers. He studied the use of the structure and system to scientifically manage human resources, and then master the talents with comprehensive skills, and used the flexible leadership style to promote the realization of the club's strategic goals, timely adjust the development strategy and organizational structure, increase the supervision of the implementation of the system, and form a complete human resources system. The organizational structure has an important influence on the Operation Management of Cheerleading Events in Yunnan Province. (3) The second key theoretical research is talent training, which is the process of educating and training talents. The selected talents generally need to be trained to become professionals required by various occupations and positions. The same is to set up a correct view of talent, make the best use of their talents, so that each talent energy to give full play to. And adopt talent quality assessment, ability assessment, develop reasonable and effective training methods and other ways to realize talent management. The study of Zhou et al. (2021, p.157) shows that the cultivation of talents is a systematic project, including both the acquisition of knowledge, the strong physique and the perfection of personality. Talent training is the key factor affecting the Operation Management of Cheerleading Events in Yunnan Province. (4) Event training is another important concept of this framework, which is to establish the needs of the event, implement and continuously improve the event Operation Management system, reduce the

risk of the event, improve the environment and improve the venue facilities, so as to improve the Operation Management mode of the event. The study of Huang (2021, p.7) shows that sports events have evolved from the nature of sports competitions, which refers to a certain scale and formal sports competitions, and have a certain influence in the society. (5) Operation Management is about the process of strategic decision-making, design, operation, maintenance and improvement of the organization operation system, fully tap social and economic benefits, carry out marketization, improve efficiency, actively play the management system and role, and provide sustainable and good development for the event. Juravich M, Salaga S and Babiak K (2017) studies the operation of the event without people. An excellent team is the basis for the good development of the event. It is found that the technical experience of the general manager and the education of the general manager are positively related to winning and efficiency. The results also illustrate the importance of obtaining elite talent.

2.2 Research Framework

According to the research topic, there are four variables in this study, and Figure 2.1 shows the schematic diagram of the model.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual model

This study established five hypotheses based on the research topic and research framework model. H1: The organizational structure and talent training of the Operation Management of Cheerleading Events are positively correlated. H2: There is a positive relationship between the organizational structure of the Cheerleading event Operation Management and the event

training. H3: There is a positive correlation between event training and Operation Management. H4: Talent training and competition training are positively correlated. H5: There is also a positive correlation between the organization structure and Operation Management of Cheerleading events.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology used in this study is a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. This method was chosen because it allows for a comprehensive exploration of the research issues and a deeper understanding of the factors affecting the Operation Management of Cheerleading events.

The first step in the research methodology is to conduct semi-structured expert in-depth interviews. In-depth interviews with experts are used to gain insight into the opinions of experts in the field. A qualitative analysis of the collected data was performed to identify key themes and patterns.

The second step of the research methodology was to design the questionnaire and collect the data. The questionnaire was designed to collect quantitative and qualitative data on the variables examined, including organisational structure, training, personnel training, event training and operational management. Data collected in the questionnaire were analyzed using statistical analysis methods, including descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, and regression analysis.

Finally, using the method of focus group interview, the paper formulated the path or plan to optimize the Operation Management of Cheerleading Events in Yunnan Province. Focus group interviews include gathering a group of stakeholders, including event Operation Management experts, event organization and management experts, experts and scholars from universities engaged in event Operation Management, event sponsors, referees, and coaches, to discuss and develop strategies to improve the Operation Management of Cheerleading events.

This study used a mixture of qualitative and quantitative research methods. The first step was a semi-structured, in-depth interview with the 13 experts. In the second step, 500 athletes were surveyed for data collection, data analysis and data synthesis. Determine the satisfaction and participation of athletes in the Operation Management of Yunnan Province Cheerleading events. Construct the influence structure model of Yunnan province Cheerleading event Operation Management. The model was evaluated through focus group discussions with 9 experts.

Semi-structured in-depth interviews with 13 experts with different experiences and views could ensure the validity and reliability of the data collected through the expert interviews. Survey participants were selected from 500 athletes by a random sampling method. According to the purpose of the study, 13 measures and 52 questions were established based on 4 study variables, adhere to the ethical rules during the questionnaire design and distribution process, and keep their information confidential.

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Qualitative analysis

This study invited 13 engaged in the field of different experts made the depth interview, for the feasibility of four dimensions variables further research, an expert in Yunnan province Cheerleading event Operation Management "organization structure" said: Yunnan province Cheerleading event mode is mainly is given priority to with campus events, through events to la la hold this project let more children and parents realize, but also make a la cao project from campus to society, the process requires all functional departments responsible, more professional guidance, rationalization of distribution and coordination between the levels. In the interview, on the variable of "talent cultivation", an expert said: After nearly ten years of development, Yunnan Province Cheerleading competition has become a brand competition in Yunnan Province, but also a national quality competition, and the success of this event is inseparable from the cultivation and participation of professional talents. In the variable of "competition training".

4.2 Quantitative studies

In this study, 500 individual questionnaires were collected, and 415 valid questionnaires were collected after excluding the invalid questionnaires, with an effective recovery rate of 100%.

4.2.1 Analysis of exploratory factors

4.2.1.1 Descriptive statistics and normality test

In this paper, the questionnaire data were analyzed using SPSS 26.0. Based on the collected questionnaires, a descriptive statistical analysis was performed, including the mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis of each observed variable, and the overall mean and standard deviation of the sample. The indicators of Organizational Structure (OZS) include specialization (SPE), hierarchical (HIE), and rationalization (RAT). The indicators of Talent Training (TLT) include ability training (ABI), quality training (QUA) and training method (TRA). Metrics for Event Training (ETT) include risk (RIS), environment (ENV), and facilities (FAC). Operational Management (OMG) indicators include benefit (BEN), marketization (MAR), efficiency (EFF) and sustainability development (SUS), averaging from 3.0 to 3.8, and kurtosis ranging from -1 to + 1, indicating that the questionnaire results of this sample follow a univariate normal distribution and can be used for confirmatory factor analysis.

4.2.2 Credit and validity test of the index system

4.2.2.1 Data reliability test

Before analyzing the survey data, it is necessary to check the measurement variables questionnaire to ensure that the measurement tool has good reliability and validity.

Table 4.1: Standard Values for Reliability Measurements

Variables	Items	Cronbach's	Total Cronbach's
BEN	4	0.802	
MAR	4	0.784	
EFF	4	0.825	
SUS	4	0.813	0.926
SPE	4	0.822	
HIE	4	0.792	
RAT	4	0.783	
RIS	4	0.830	
ENV	4	0.804	
FAC	4	0.828	
QUA	4	0.764	
ABI	4	0.720	
MAR	4	0.784	

Reliability is reliability, which refers to the results of the consistency and stability of the questionnaire test excluding systematic errors. In general, consistency indicates whether the results are plausible. Although systematic error has little impact on reliability, it can also affect the accuracy measurement, resulting to inconsistency of measurement results. The questionnaire test results may reduce the reliability.

The higher the reliability coefficient, the more consistent, stable and reliable the results of the questionnaire test. The common methods of reliability analysis are: retest reliability method, complex reliability method, and half reliability method and clone Bach coefficient. As a common method for visual reliability testing, the cloned Bach coefficient overcomes the inherent defects of some methods. Therefore, the cloned Bach reliability coefficient was used for reliability analysis. In terms of measures, the larger the coefficient is, the more reliable the questionnaire is.

Through the reliability analysis of the items, the above table shows that each dimension and quantity are greater than 0.7, which indicates that the reliability coefficient of the questionnaire data is high, the questionnaire is reliable, the coefficient is concentrated, and the reliability coefficient fluctuates less. Therefore, there is no need to delete the index and can be further analyzed.

This study examined the reliability of the findings on the effects using SPSS 26.0. As shown in Table 4.1, the Cronbach "coefficient of each measured variable is between 0.72 and 0.86, and the overall Cronbach" coefficient of this scale is 0.926, indicating the good internal consistency of the scale, which partly reflects the reliability of the measured scale in this study, and provides a strong guarantee for the validity of the subsequent study results.

4.2.2.2 Data validity test

Data validity refers to the restriction from content to quantity of data entered to a cell or cell region. For eligible data, allowed to input and not for non-eligible data. In this way, the system can be used to check the correct validity of the data to avoid incorrect data entry.

Data (data) is the result of fact or observation, the logical induction of objective things, and the unprocessed raw material used to represent objective things. Data can be continuous values, such as sound, images, and are called analog data. It can also be discrete, such as symbols, text, called digital data.

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

EFA is a technique used to find out the essential structure of multivariate observation variables and to deal with dimension reduction. Therefore, EFA can synthesize the variables with complex relationships into a few core factors. The purpose of EFA is to explore the factors or latent variables that the measurement topic should belong to.

Validity analysis of the questionnaire data

The EFA method was used to test the characteristic validity of the survey questionnaire. EFA can effectively identify the essential structure of multivariate observation variables, and can reduce the dimension of multivariate observation variables by clustering the variables with complex relationships into several core factors. Before factor analysis, it is necessary to conduct Bartlett sphere test on the questionnaire data and measure the KMO (Kaiser Meyer Olkin) value. It is generally considered that the KMO value is above 0.7, and the significance level of spherical test reaches the significance requirement of two-tailed test, so as to show that the questionnaire data is suitable for factor analysis.

Table 4.2: KMO and Bartlett's Sphericity Test

KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.897
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	9403.494
	df	1326
	Sig.	0.000

EFA of 52 measurement items of operational management model by SPSS26.0, KMO and Bartlett spherical test results in Table 4.2 show that KMO = 0.897 (greater than 0.7), the approximate square value of Bartlett spherical test is 9403.494, degree of freedom (df) is 1326, significance (Sig.) = 0.000 (very significant), indicating that the assumption of independent of each variable is not true, and the data concentration measured by the questionnaire is good, which is suitable for factor analysis.

4.2.3 Correlation analysis between the variables

Table 4.3: Average of variance extracted (AVE)

Variables	Items	AVE
BEN	4	0.5409
MAR	4	0.4219
EFF	4	0.4864
SUS	4	0.4915
SPE	4	0.5626
HIE	4	0.5319
RAT	4	0.5068
RIS	4	0.5414
ENV	4	0.5252
FAC	4	0.5491
QUA	4	0.4604
ABI	4	0.4602
MET	4	0.5967

Table 4.4: Correlation analysis between variables

	BEN	MAR	EFF	SUS	SPE	HIE	RAT	RIS	ENV	FAC	QUA	ABI	MET
BEN	1												
MAR	.428**	1											
EFF	.455**	.553**	1										
SUS	.528**	.620**	.608**	1									
SPE	.236**	.256**	.295**	.308**	1								
HIE	.165**	.248**	.292**	.318**	.473**	1							
RAT	.228**	.220**	.318**	.275**	.504**	.581**	1						
RIS	.300**	.305**	.318**	.368**	.152**	.153**	.222**	1					
ENV	.305**	.302**	.340**	.384**	.186**	.188**	.156**	.537**	1				
FAC	.303**	.294**	.322**	.339**	.167**	.240**	.236**	.535**	.447**	1			
QUA	.321**	.317**	.338**	.390**	.334**	.296**	.223**	.351**	.363**	.356**	1		
ABI	.291**	.277**	.277**	.368**	.282**	.338**	.258**	.263**	.314**	.308**	.707**	1	
MET	.217**	.215**	.200**	.266**	.345**	.280**	.258**	.192**	.223**	.224**	.631**	.668**	1

** : The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

The results of the confirmatory factor analysis of the measurement model are shown in Table 4.3, which shows that the standardized factor load of 13 latent variables is greater than 0.4, and the factor coefficient is very significant ($p= 0.000$), indicating that the measurement model has strong explanatory power; the average variance extraction (AVE) of 13 latent variables is 0.4219, indicating that the measurement model has good internal consistency (reliability) and aggregate validity.

In addition, the absolute values of the correlation coefficient between the potential variables shown in Table 4.4 are significantly smaller than the AVE square root value of the potential variables (the value highlighted in the diagonal in the matrix), indicating that the measurement model has good differential validity, that is, the characteristics of each potential

variable are significantly different from other potential variables. Comprehensive above test results, Yunnan province Cheerleading event Operation Management factors of measurement model of fit is good, and the measurement model has good reliability and validity, can be based on the measurement model and sample data theory hypothesis structure model analysis, to test the path relationship between the potential variables, and verify the proposed theoretical hypothesis is established.

4.2.4 Standardized factor loading coefficients

Table 4.5: Fitting Indicators for Variable Models (Full Model)

Norm	CMIN/DF	TLI	GFI	CFI	AGFI	RMSEA
SD	<3	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	<0.08
NB	1.559		0.968	0.984	0.950	0.037

Table 4.5 shows the model fit for the confirmatory factor analysis. Model fitting indicators do not have to be fully displayed, only a few common indicators are displayed. Secondly, most of the model fit indicators meet the standard, which means that the model fits well.

In Table 4.5, the CMIN and DF of the model are associated with the sample size and the complexity of the model. There is no good standard for this indicator, and it is usually just shown. CMIN / DF is the relative ratio of chi-square to degree of freedom, with <3 indicating a good fit. TLI, GFI, CFI, and AGFI > 0.9 indicate that the model fit. RMSEA <0.08 indicates a good fit. All of the above indicators meet the standards. After comprehensive consideration, the fit of the model is very ideal.

4.2.5 Regarding the aggregated effectiveness of the variables

Table 4.6: Model AVE and CR Indicator Results

Factor	Mean variance-extracted AVE values	Combined reliability CR value
Organizational Structure (OZS)	0.5564	0.7889
Talent Training (TLT)	0.5981	0.8170
Event Training (ETT)	0.6282	0.8343
Operation Management (OMG)	0.6352	0.8732

AVE value = mean (loading square is sum), CR value = $\frac{\text{Sum}(\text{load})^2}{\text{Sum}(\text{load})^2 + \text{sum}(e)}$, the loading value is the standardized loading coefficient and e is the standard residual loading coefficient. In general, aggregate validity is high when AVE is greater than 0.5 and CR value is greater than 0.7. In Table 4.6, the AVE values of the four dimensions are greater than 0.5, and the CR values are greater than 0.7, indicating the good aggregation (convergence) effectiveness of the analyzed data.

4.2.6 Discriminant validity

Table 4.7: Differentiation validity: Pearson correlation and AVE square root value

	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Factor4
Talent Development (TDL)	0.773			
Organizational Structure (OZS)	0.476	0.751		
Event Training (ETT)	0.499	0.362	0.793	
Operation Management (OMG)	0.493	0.493	0.609	0.797

Note: Bold diagonal numbers are AVE square root values

The diagonal lines in Table 4.7 show AVE square root values and the rest are Pearson's correlation coefficient. The AVE square root value can represent the "aggregation degree" of the factor, and the correlation coefficient represents the correlation. If the factor "aggregation" is strong (significantly stronger than the absolute value of the) correlation coefficient with other factors. If the AVE square root value of a factor is greater than the absolute value of the correlation coefficient between that factor and another factor. And all the factors showed such a conclusion, indicating a good discrimination validity. In Table 4.7, the AVE square root value of talent cultivation is 0.773, which is greater than the maximum value of the correlation coefficient between absolute factors, indicating that the differentiation validity is optimal.

The AVE square root value of the tissue structure is 0.751, which is greater than the maximum value of the correlation coefficient of 0.476, indicating the optimal discrimination validity. The AVE square root value of field training was 0.793, which is greater than the maximum correlation coefficient of 0.499, indicating the optimal discriminatory validity. The AVE square root value of Operation Management is 0.797, which is greater than the maximum value of the absolute cross-relation number of 0.493, which means the best discriminatory validity.

4.2.7 Indirect effects

The path (H6) of the effect value is 0.104, total effect 0.469, total effect 22.17%, total indirect effect 0.171, total indirect effect 60.82%, Bias-corrected percentile method interval 0.055-0.184, no 0, indicating a significant indirect effect. The path (H7) of the effect value was 0.067, the total effect was 14.29%, the total indirect effect was 0.171, the total indirect effect was 39.18%, Bias-corrected percentile method interval-0.005-0.143, including 0, which means that its indirect effect was not significant.

4.2.8 Hypothesis verification

The hypothesis validation $T > 1.96$, $P < 0.05$ hypothesis holds. Table 4.23 Data analysis, the T value of pathway (H1) $OZS \rightarrow TLT$ is 7.566, > 1.96 , and the P-value is < 0.05 , indicating that the hypothesis is true. The T value of the path (H2) $OZS \rightarrow ETT$ is 2.02, > 1.96 , and the P-

value is 0.043, <0.05 , indicating that the assumption is true. The T value of path (H3) ETT→OMG is 7.009, >1.96 and P value <0.05 , indicating that the assumption is true. The T value of path (H4) TLT→ETT is 6.371, >1.96 , and P value <0.05 indicates that the assumption is true. The T value of path (H5) OZS→OMG is 5.06, >1.96 and P value <0.05 , indicating that the hypothesis is true.

4.3 Qualitative study

The experts at the meeting expressed full recognition for the research model, and the relationship between each variable and the hypothesis was a positive relationship, which has a positive impact on the Operation Management system of the event. After the verification of the equation model, the organizational structure does have an important influence on the model. One expert in the Operation Management of the sports event requires the participation of professional organization, reasonable organization structure, and the rationality and professionalism of the organizational structure of the functional departments of the event can better make the event proceed smoothly.

Equation model verification talent training is an important factor affecting the model, among which related experts say: to get more people to participate in the project, the training of related talent is very important; and experts say: talent training determines the development of the project.

Through the verification of the equation model, this variable plays a very important role in the model. Some experts say that the operation of the event requires human, material and financial investment, as well as risk assessment and environmental assessment. The experts at the meeting also further put forward higher requirements for the model, hoping to integrate the current digital age with the management system in the future research.

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

5.1 Conclusion

The effective organizational structure is consistent with the results of the influence of system management on the Operation Management results of Cheerleading events. In particular, it emphasizes the important theoretical support for the research of talent training.

The key role of specialization, hierarchy and rationalization in organizational structure is consistent with our findings on the importance of organizational structure in Cheerleading events, emphasizing that specialization, hierarchy and rationalization in the organizational environment. The paper puts forward the challenges and opportunities facing the Operation Management of Yunnan Province Cheerleading events, and emphasizes the necessity of talent cultivation.

The research focuses on the Operation Management of the event. The research discusses the existence of the event life of a project and focuses on the Operation Management, so that the event can be carried out continuously. This view is crucial to understanding the pattern of the Operation Management of Cheerleading events. It emphasizes the complexity of the

event management system and the need for multi-faceted development, a comprehensive understanding that is crucial to managing the continued development of Cheerleading Events and challenging brand building.

The development of the Operation Management of Cheerleading Events in Yunnan province should follow the characteristics of the project and rely closely on the development of school sports. Emphasize that the selection is in line with the age characteristics of Cheerleading programs, aiming to cultivate well-rounded students, and in line with the practice of China's national fitness concept.

5.2 Discussions

In the era of rapid development of science and technology, the intervention of information means makes more people pay attention to the relevant events, makes the Cheerleading project quickly into people's vision, but also makes more parents see the advantages of the project, so that more students participate. As Zhu and Xu (2020, p.218) believes that the sustainable development of Cheerleading Events IP is to continuously improve the level of IP cultural products of Cheerleading events, expand the value chain of IP products, and extend the life cycle of IP products of Cheerleading events. The impact of such a form on organizational structural change cannot be ignored because it establishes the way the project interacts with its participants and how these participants gain perception and recognition.

Chen (2023) believes that the construction of talent echelon is a key work in the development of the group, which is related to the long-term development of the enterprise. The group should actively introduce and train talents, especially the introduction of high-quality talents, so as to inject new blood into the enterprise, enhance the overall competitiveness of the enterprise, and improve the management ability.

Li (2021) proposed that the Cheerleading training market should provide diversified training activities to meet the needs of different objects; promote international and domestic exchanges, improve the level of training instructors, enrich the training content; limit the age of colorful star class, and expand the scope of participating groups as the main development path. When studying the role of event training, Fang and Zhou (2014) believes that the most important thing in the 21st century is talents, and the training and transportation of talents in universities is also one of the basic characteristics of the 13th Five-Year Plan of sports. The same is true of the Cheerleading project, to put the talent training on the top priority, explore the Cheerleading talent market, strengthen communication, so as to accelerate the overall development of the Cheerleading movement.

5.3 Suggestions

5.3.1 Strengthen the event Operation Management planning.

The development of Cheerleading Events in Yunnan province is the most dynamic and potential. It is suggested to strengthen the upgrading and development mode according to the research model, and strengthen the Operation Management of the competition.

5.3.2 Strengthen all aspects of operation and upgrading.

In addition to striving for the relevant government departments to increase capital investment, as the event operator, we should also develop the surrounding products of the Cheerleading event to improve the hematopoietic ability of the event.

5.3.3 Build the Talent Training for Cheerleading Event Operation.

Through the establishment of a complete training mechanism for Cheerleading event talents, vigorously cultivate high-quality Cheerleading event related staff. Suggest related colleges and universities, from the perspective of the talent training plan reform, through university-enterprise cooperation in the curriculum management operation training.

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